

ReNEW

D5.1 Communication and dissemination plan

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Funded by
the European Union

Document Info

Document	
Document identifier	D5.1
Due Date of Delivery to EC	00-00-2022
Actual Date of Delivery to EC	00-00-2022
Dissemination level	3
Work package	WP5

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Control Sheet			
Version	Date	Editor	Summary of Modifications
Version 0.1	15/02/2023	Andrea Hrzic, Magellan Association	First draft and outline of all chapters
Version 0.2	17/02/2023	Iryna Moroz, Magellan Association	Revision of Chapters 5 and 6, Gender balance and dimension topic
Version 0.3	19/02/2023	Anastasiya Azarko, PNO	Chapter 2
Version 0.4	19/02/2023	Yuliya Sahitava, IWT	Chapter 8 revision
Version 0.5	20/02/2023	Andrea Hrzic, Magellan Association	Revision of all chapters, final draft
Version 0.6	24/02/2023	Andrea Hrzic, Magellan Association Anastasiya Azarko, PNO	Comments addressed by reviewers, reformatting of layout and headings
Version 0.7	28/02/2023	Andrea Hrzic, Magellan Association	Compliance table added

Acronyms and Abreviations

Acronym / Abreviation	Meaning
AKKA	AKKA technologies
CEF	Connecting Europe Facility
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
D	Deliverable
DG RTD	Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GE	Gender Equality
GEP(s)	Gender Equality Plan(s)
GRIWT	Green Resilient Inland Waterways
INLE	INLECOM
IP	Intellectual Property
IWW	Inland Waterways
KPI(s)	Key Performance Indicator(s)
LL(s)	Living Lab(s)
M	Month
MAG	Magellan Association
PNO	PNO Group
R	Result
RIS	River Information System
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
WP(s)	Work Package(s)

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Executive Summary

The D5.1 Communication and dissemination plan is an update of the initial strategy proposed at the proposal stage.

The purpose of the document is to provide clear guidelines and strategy on how to communicate and disseminate the ReNEW goals and objectives in the best possible way. The plan serves as a one-stop-shop for partners with information on the project brand identity, communication tools that can be used and in what ways as well as important lists of dates and events which might be useful to further promote ReNEW and its results.

The document describes the Communication and Dissemination (C&D) tools in detail including visual identity, website, social media, printed materials, presentation, videos, newsletter and press and media. A preliminary list of events and workshops to be organised during the project's life are described in Chapter 4. These tools and channels are accompanied with the Key Performance Indicators at the end of the document in order to monitor and account for the impact of this strategy.

The roles and responsibilities of each partner are described in the chapter "Management" while the cross-cooperation with other projects is further described in the final chapter.

This strategy is a living document and will be revised as the project reaches its first milestones and results.

1. Communication objectives

1.1 ReNEW Background

As climate change severely affects the performance of IWT operations, the priority is to create and test new solutions for climate-neutral and climate-resilient IWT.

IWT system resilience is essentially co-dependent on infrastructure and barge/fleet reliability, maintainability, and fault tolerance. It embraces the sectors' key priorities: sustainable infrastructure adjustments, environmental friendliness and competitiveness of vessel fleet, digitalisation, integration of IWT in multimodal transport chains, and securing the availability of skilled workers.

The European Commission sees the digitalisation of the Transport sector as a primary enabler of smart solutions for sustainable transport that can support resilience solutions and deliver economic, environmental, and societal benefits.

From an IWT resilience perspective, particularly important is the improved interaction between infrastructure management systems and barge operations. Combining the technological advantages of digitalisation and automation, autonomous barges, including autonomous infrastructure interaction, provide economic benefits to revolutionise the future IWT system whilst delivering climate-neutral and climate-resilient IWT services.

However, progress in adopting innovation by the IWT sector, and achieving the associated resilience and decarbonisation goals, will be unrestricted by technology limitations rather than systemic challenges affecting the European IWT digital and energy transition.

Historically, the waterborne sector has exhibited a passive and conservative posture towards innovation, as well as a reluctance to digitalise "best practices". In IWT, this is principally owed to conventional "ways of operating" by barge skippers/owners, resulting in a highly ageing, inefficient fleet with unreliable and polluting operations.

To address these challenges, it is necessary to incentivise innovations across the dimensions outlined above and provide robust validation of how and where innovation can support the transition to a sustainable, resilient, high-efficiency IWT system.

In response to the abovementioned challenges and shortcomings, ReNEW will deliver:

1. A decision-support framework including Resilience and Sustainability Quantification supporting the strategic planning and operational optimisation of Green Resilient IWT (GRIWT).

2. Innovative infrastructure resilience and sustainability solutions targeting rapid deployment after disruptive events to create new provisional links to other transport modes and building on autonomy developments and maturing green energy options.
3. A Green Resilient IWT Dataspace and Digital Twin primarily provide data sharing between infrastructure monitoring, RIS and traffic management, and emergency systems and climate solutions.
4. Four Living Labs designed to provide exemplars from LLs focusing on integrated IW and hinterland infrastructure [Gent-urban, Douro-corridor, Netherlands–national/EU network perspectives] to a LL addressing specifically inland waterway resilience.
5. The ReNEW Outreach and Upscale program designed to maximise impact pathways spearheaded by the European Inland Waterways (IWT) Transport Platform and industry clusters as well as leading industry innovators.

1.1.1 Mapping the ReNEW Output

The following table (Table 1) maps the ReNEW’s Grant Agreement (GA) commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work to perform.

Table 1 Adherence to ReNEW’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

Deliverable D5.1	
D5.1: Dissemination and Communication Report [MAG] [A=M6; B=M18; C=M30; D=M36]	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A) Stakeholders Analysis and Innovation Maps, an intelligence study by PNO to build the ground for the dissemination plan. It will include disaggregated data and a gender analysis among the innovators in the sector. Project communication and dissemination Strategy by MAG; B) Periodic Activities Report. C) C) Final Report. 	

ReNEW GA Element Title	ReNEW GA Element Outline	Respective Document Chapter (s) and Description
ST5.1.1 Dissemination & Communication plan, material and website	<p>Detailed plan for communication and dissemination to achieve the ambitions of ReNEW.</p> <p>Key input will be a stakeholder mapping developed by PNO (M6) for reaching out the targeted audiences, while key outcomes will</p>	<p>The stakeholder mapping is described in Chapter 2</p> <p>Project promotion profile with logo, design and templates is description in Chapter 3. Communication and</p>

	<p>be presented in the form of news articles, reports, presentations etc.</p> <p>Create a project promotion profile with logo, design manual and templates for an attractive visual identity. In addition, posters, one-pagers and flyers will be produced to be used at relevant events.</p> <p>Furthermore, the project website will be created and maintained from the beginning of the project and after its lifetime. ReNEW will have accounts in several social media integrated into the project website.</p> <p>Two (2) professional videos highlighting the LLs innovations, their challenges, their vision and expected outcomes will be produced.</p>	<p>dissemination tools and in the relevant subchapter 3.1 Visual Identity.</p> <p>The project website and social media accounts are described in Chapter 3, Subchapter 3.2 Website, while the printed materials such as flyers and roll ups are in subchapter 3.6.</p> <p>Videos are further described in subchapter 3.7</p>
<p>ST5.1.2 Perform networking, alliance across projects, and the ReNEW Liaison and Clustering activities</p>	<p>Ensure the coordination and alignment with other H2020/Horizon Europe & CEF projects in EU and create the strategy and initiate discussions to share relevant experiences among similar projects.</p> <p>Liaise with the ALICE European Technology Platform, with specific interest to the Corridors, Hubs and Synchro-modality thematic group (TG2) about Climate Resilient Transport Networks (CRTN), and with other initiatives, connect and invite related projects to the discussions of focused ReNEW workshops or webinars during which outputs of the projects can be aligned and potential synergies identified.</p> <p>Driven by the Advisory Board, at the beginning of the project the ReNEW stakeholders Cluster, formed to include infrastructure managers operators and authorities from all IWT segments across the relevant EU's geographic areas to both get valuable input as regards the technical, social, environmental, legal and economic impacts, and to better facilitate the dissemination of the project results.</p> <p>Identify, and coordinate the participation in exhibitions and fairs. Communication packages for LLs and promotional events will be carried out, and a major EU conference will be delivered in M24.</p>	<p>These objectives are covered mainly in chapters 4 and 8 even though they are mentioned also in Chapter 2 and Chapter 1. Coordination and alignment with other project is in detail described in Chapter 8 Cross-cooperation with other project.</p> <p>A preliminary list of external events is included in Chapter 4 as well as a description of workshops to be organised by ReNEW.</p>

1.2 Communication goals

In ReNEW, communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities will aim to:

- i) guarantee proper diffusion of knowledge and project results towards stakeholders along the whole relevant value chain, including interested authorities, regulatory bodies, workers, and the general public, according to the case.
- ii) facilitate the exchange of information and interaction with targeted stakeholders to increase the chance to reach the market in due time after the end of the project;
- iii) secure maximum impact fostering the adoption of project results, capacity building and max-impact positioning before relevant decision-makers and stakeholders.

Objective 5

ReNEW Outreach and Upscale designed to maximise impact pathways through effective Communications Innovation management, Commercialisation and Capacity building and policy Recommendation.

Expected results of the Outreach and Upscale Work Package

The main results of Objective 5 are listed below:

R18. Dissemination of key outcomes through relevant media and communication packages, networking with other past and current EC-funded projects and liaison activities including the ReNEW stakeholders' Cluster with advisory and user groups will be formed to include infrastructure managers operators and authorities from all IWT segments across the relevant EU's geographic areas.

R19. Innovation management, IP Management and IP Protection (Patent Filings protecting commercial advantages for the EU IWT sector) and market sector analysis, business modelling and strategy for commercialisation.

R20. Capacity building from the project results and outputs including Training Workshops and a comprehensive ReNEW Guide with steps to move from planning, implementation, replication and scale-up linked with awareness, results communication, feedback and education transferability activities for EU's IWT actors

R21. Policy recommendations on ReNEW scale-up in the IWT community.

R22. Stakeholders' innovation mapping with included a gender equality disaggregated analysis

The ReNEW communication activities will be planned and developed following the communication objectives to be established in WP5. The main goal of the communication activities will be to enable a structured and targeted interaction between the stakeholders within the Consortium and externally and the identified target audiences, as well as disseminating the project results effectively. For this

purpose, the C&D activities are clearly outlined in this document. The approach ensures that the project partners have a clear agreement on the vision regarding communication and objectives, alongside the different roles and responsibilities. ReNEW will employ a strong public relations communications method, ensuring that the messages to be articulated are consistent at all times where each partner is responsible to communicate the project through their networks. Finally, the project will deploy a great variety of communication activities through specific, pre-identified communication channels with a particular emphasis to the digitalisation.

A series of Dissemination and Communication elements will address the following issues:

- Overall Communication and Dissemination strategy and related expected results, timing of actions and KPI.
- Key messages to convey to each segment of the target audience.
- Leading principles of engagement for each segment of the target audience for each Partner.
- Visual Identity and related layouts guidelines and templates.
- Digital Tools for proper Dissemination and Communication activities.
- Project events / workshops / symposium (virtual & physical) as tools for proper Dissemination and Communication.

A mix of different communication tools and channels will be used for different target groups (Chapter 4) in order to communicate the key messages of the project. Preliminary key messages of the project objectives and potential outcomes have already been identified above in ReNEW background, however, more key messages related to the impact targets of the call are identified below:

- 1. ReNEW aims to help sustaining IWT network capacities in Inland Waterways at levels not falling below 50% by improving navigability conditions and advancing resilience*
- 2. ReNEW will enhance land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events while aiming to maintain network capacities to 80% levels during the disruptions.*
- 3. ReNEW will contribute to the sustainability of the IWT systems network promoting modal shift, supporting the EU goals for 20% increase for Inland Waterways.*
- 4. ReNEW will accelerate resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport and logistics networks operating on these infrastructures.*
- 5. ReNEW will increase the use of recycled materials within or across transport modes by at least 30% in the Ghent Living Lab.*
- 6. ReNEW will reduce environmental impact (emissions, soil/water pollution, degradation of ecosystems and fragmentation of habitats) during construction, maintenance, operation and decommissioning of the infrastructure in line with the EU environmental legislation.*

More key messages will be defined during the duration of the project and the creation of the ReNEW printed materials (see Chapter 5).

2. Target audiences

2.1 Value Chain

The ReNEW project aims to promote the development of sustainable, resilient, and innovative inland waterway transport systems in the EU. In this context, the value chain plays a critical role in understanding the various stages and players involved in bringing new technologies and services to market. The ReNEW value chain includes the design and development of smart and green inland waterway vessels, the integration of resilient and energy-efficient technologies, the deployment of networked and intelligent transport systems, and the provision of support services to the end-users. By analysing the ReNEW value chain, we can identify opportunities for innovation, sustainability, and circularity, as well as strategies for optimising the value chain to reduce costs, increase efficiency, and promote competitiveness in the market.

A specific value chain has been created for the ReNEW project to reflect the various activities carried out by its partners in promoting the decarbonisation of inland waterways transportation and making the sector more sustainable and resilient. The value chain encompasses all possible actions and actors involved in this process and is divided into two blocks: one related to providers of green and resilient IWT solutions, and the other related to infrastructures that will utilise the developed solutions. The identified steps of the value chain are listed and explained below, with a particular focus on the roles played by the ReNEW partners:

- **Green and resilient IWT software developers:** all the developers of software technologies aiming to digitalise inland waterways transportation sectors are involved and have been divided into four sub-categories:
 1. **Digital twin:** the developers (both on R&D and private sides) of the digital twin, simulation and modelling solutions applied to inland waterways transportation (IMEC, IRT SystemX);
 2. **Traffic/Navigation management:** the developers (both on the R&D and private sides) of ICT solutions related to the route planning and predicting and evaluating factors (e.g. extreme events) that influence the inland waterways navigation (ISL, Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Konneckta, 4Shipping);
 3. **IoT/Connectivity:** the developers (both on R&D and private sides) of internet of things solutions aiming to improve connectivity between the various infrastructures in inland waterways (ICCS, Konneckta, AKKA Technologies);
 4. **Autonomy:** the developers (both on R&D and private sides) of software allowing ships to move autonomously and automating the activities carried out in IWT infrastructures (SINTEF);

- **Systems engineering and integration:** who provides engineering and integration services for exploiting the digital solutions in the IWT infrastructures has been considered and divided into five sub-categories:
 1. **Ship and pontoon design:** who provides design services for building ships and pontoons, comprising Naval Architecture (University of Galati, Zulu Associates);
 2. **Shipyards:** who builds ships for inland navigation;
 3. **Remote control centres:** who manages and operates control centres for operating an autonomous ship remotely, integrating the various developed digital solutions in a unique platform (Seafar NV, SINTEF);
 4. **Infrastructure systems engineering:** who provides engineering services for the various infrastructures equipment and systems (mooring, docking, locking, etc.), allowing them to be automatic;
 5. **Power supply:** who provides solutions related to the integration and the adoption of green energy in inland waterways transportation, such as charging stations, alternative propulsions, hydrogen fuel cells, batteries, etc.;

- **Infrastructures management:** all the operators and managers of the various infrastructures present in the inland waterways transportation are considered, and divided in:
 - a) **Fixed:** the managers and operators of all fixed infrastructure, such as ports, terminals or hinterland hubs (ADPL - Administração dos Portos do Douro, Leixões e Viana do Castelo, SA)
 - b) **Mobile:** this category considers all the actors related to the transport and logistics placed in inland waterways, such as ship owners (Zulu Associates), ship managers/operators and shippers.

Besides the main stakeholder categories above mentioned and described, it was identified several horizontal stakeholders that play a transversal role along the IWT-identified value chain:

- **Investors/Financiers:** who provide investments or funding within the IW sectors for implementing its digitalisation (Zulu Associates);
- **Policymakers and regulators:** the entities which regulate the sector;
- **Sector associations:** the clusters and associations representing the actors involved in inland waterways transportation (MAGELLAN, European IWT Platform, VIL, OHB);
- **Classification, risk management and insurance companies:** the companies providing classification and certification activities, risk analysis and management, and insurance services within the IW sector (Research Driven Solutions Limited);
- **Other:** all the other organisations providing services for improving, exploiting and disseminating the solutions developed for making the greener and more resilient IWT, such as consultancy, LCA and other impacts analysis, etc. (SINTEF, PANTEIA, VLTN, PNO, INLECOM).

Below, there is the value chain concept as described above, including one with partners' logos representing the activities carried out in ReNEW project.

Figure 1 ReNEW value chain

2.2 Stakeholder analysis

The Innovation component of the stakeholder's analysis is a form of (technological) intelligence that PNO performs intending to identify the main players in a specific market segment or value chain, their role in that value chain, and their contribution to innovations, inventions or business in a particular sector. The benefit of the stakeholder analysis to interested parties is that it provides them with a helicopter view on the most active stakeholders (mostly industry) related to a specific market segment for the purpose of:

- Finding potential partners for business collaborations and/or funding applications.
- Identifying potentially interesting innovations to integrate in their products or innovation plans (open innovation).
- Spotting innovation trends, incumbent or dis-investing players and competitors.
- Market analysis and exploitation strategies.

Using the [PNO's tool WheesBee](#) and considering the main objectives of the ReNEW, the list of **total of 131 European-funded projects** (starting date from 01/01/2014) selected for building the innovation ecosystem related to ReNEW project was created. The selection is guided by the projects mentioned in the proposal in which ReNEW partners have participated.

The projects identified have been mapped, taking into account, on the one hand, the project focus and, on the other hand, the project output. Moreover, given the huge amount of projects identified, there were mapped projects financed by the H2020 and HORIZON programs, as several CEF, INTERREG and National projects that are similar in theme to ReNEW.

Concerning the Project Focus, we identified the following three categories:

- **TRANSPORT & LOGISTICS IN GENERAL:** this category encompasses projects that aim to promote solutions and services in the broader transport and logistics sector, including initiatives for the IWT.
- **INLAND WATERWAYS TRANSPORT (IWT):** this category includes those projects that arise to promote solutions to improve and further develop the IWT sector, specifically.
- **IWT + CONNECTION WITH OTHER MODES OF TRANSPORT:** the projects mapped within this category aim to promote the IWT sector by making it more efficient in terms of logistics by promoting interconnected systems by fostering Synchromodality and multimodality.

Regarding the macro-category Project Output, three main application areas were identified.

The macro-category Project Output of the ReNEW project was defined based on its objectives, the desired technologies to be developed, and its intended connections with similar projects, where there we identified four main categories:

1. **Match-making/Data sharing platform:** this area includes those projects that aim to foster networking among key stakeholders in the sector through match-making and knowledge-sharing platforms.
2. **Mobile Infrastructure Digitalisation/Resilience:** this category maps those projects whose primary purpose is the development of technological solutions for mobile infrastructure, such as cargo, vessels, and barges.
3. **Fixed Infrastructure Digitalisation/Resilience:** this category includes projects that promote solutions to digitise and automate the shore infrastructure and its main components and activities such as ports, terminals, and cargo handling. Technologies under this category may concern automated and connected driving, alternative power supply solutions/propulsion systems, and information systems aimed at better data sharing and integration solutions.
4. **Fixed-Mobile Infrastructure Digitalisation/Resilience:** this category includes those projects that aim to make the IWT sector greener and more resilient by promoting solutions for both categories described above.

Figure 2 EU-funded projects mapping

The subsequent stage involves analysing and describing participant organisations in the selected projects to position them in the ReNEW project's created value chain. The objective is to identify and extract as many potential stakeholders as possible within the project's supply chain. To achieve this, the activities performed by each organisation in each project, as well as their websites, are carefully analysed to gain a comprehensive understanding of their expertise. This process is crucial in identifying key stakeholders who can contribute significantly to the project's success.

A total of 1381 participants, some of whom participated in multiple projects, were identified from the selected projects. These organisations can be positioned in the value chain as potential stakeholders of the ReNEW project. To determine their roles and expertise, each participant was analysed based on their involvement in the selected projects, resulting in around 560 potential stakeholders.

The most active ones (those with more participations in the selected projects) per each value chain category identified are represented in the Figure 3.

Figure 3 ReNEW potential stakeholders

With the ReNEW potential stakeholders mapped, the project also relies on the support of its 24 partners, which are relevant entities for the community building. In order to achieve the project’s communication and dissemination goals, as described in the previous chapter, it is important to establish to whom we want to spread the message.

The approach to be employed focuses on the implementation of several targeted campaigns, directed at the different project target groups, as seen in figure 4, which will ensure that the project partners have a clear agreement on the vision regarding communication and objectives, alongside the different roles and responsibilities.

IWT authorities and infrastructure managers	European fluvial ports involved in the Living Labs, other port operators	Barges Operators
IWT shippers	Green and Resilient IWT solution providers	EU and national government policy makers
Shipyards	General audience, citizens	European Environmental Agencies

Figure 4 ReNEW audience

To conclude this chapter, the next course of action involves classifying the identified stakeholders based on their diverse backgrounds, position in the Value Chain, and other relevant characteristics. With over 100 R&D-funded projects and a significant number of participants involved, it is crucial to select and describe the most significant network possible carefully. This process will aid in understanding the stakeholders' roles and relationships and provide valuable insights into the overall dynamics of the project.

2.3 Gender balance and Gender dimension

Gender plays a key role in the economic, social, daily and private lives of individuals and societies. Therefore, it is necessary to recognise how gender and sex influence those aspects and the benefits of it.

The European Commission is committed to promoting gender equality in all sectors. In the research and innovation (R&I) sector, specific policies and actions to promote gender equality and overcome barriers have been adopted, such as the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation: Horizon Europe (2021-2027), and within the European Research Area.

According to the EC, the integration of gender balance and gender dimension in R&I brought improvements in the scientific process. The questioning of gender stereotypes leads to a greater

understanding of the gender needs, behaviours and attitudes. Therefore, the social relevance of the knowledge, technologies and innovations they produce is enhanced, contributing to a better quality of the production of goods and services (Gendered Innovations 2). Therefore, the development and implementation of gender equality measures in research require not only the equal access to all areas in positions and in decision-making bodies, increasing women’s participation in scientific research, but also eliminate structural barriers by integrating gender into research content and process.

This integrated approach towards R&I enhance the overall quality, diversity and excellency of the research, offering more creative, effective and innovative solutions, paving the way to a more sustainable and inclusive growth, increasing the business opportunities.

Even with such commitments, progress in this field continues to be slow with persisting gaps and inequalities. When it comes to gender balance, women are still under-represented in research and innovation careers (EC’s She Figures 2021 Report), with only 22% of women in the transport sector, and the integration of the gender dimension in R&I continues encountering some resistance.

In ReNEW, a gender balance analysis was conducted though the 24 consortium partners. Currently, 6 months-in to the project, there are, in total 51 females in the workplace, 27 of which are researchers, vs. 100 males, of which 51 are researchers. Out

of 14 partners with research teams, only two have a gender balance. The gender balance in the consortium will be monitored within the lifetime of the project.

In order to meet the project’s objectives and expected results, ReNEW aims to go beyond the state-of-art, through the incorporation of a holistic perspective and a multidisciplinary and inclusive approach. To do so, it is relevant to consider inequalities in the team and that gender issues are not missed or poorly addressed, since it may lead to partial or potentially biased research results that affect the needs and issues in the transportation field.

Figure 6 Total number female vs male in workplace

Figure 5 Number of female vs male researchers

ReNEW will adopt a co-creation approach (e.g., Figure 7) by assessing the possible project's impact on gender issues by spotting gender biases or any possible implications that would differently affect women and men during the project and in a scenario where the project impacts are reached. This will be done by setting up a specific Gender Equality assessment workshop (based on the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) framework. Emerging topics – if any – arise related to gender, they will be monitored as specific project's risks to be mitigated. PNO will deploy specific experts from NEHEM (part of the PNO group) to run such workshop, consistently monitoring this topic.

Figure 7 Approach to GE (Source "Gendered innovations 2: How inclusive analysis contributes to research and Innovation")

A survey will be conducted and shared across ReNEW partners in order to understand the perspective they hold towards the concept of the gender dimension and on how to integrate gender in the project. Based on the results, the workshop will serve as key to capacity building, deepening the knowledge about the topic, the benefits and how to overcome possible difficulties. This approach is based on the DG RTD report "Monitoring Progress towards Gender Equality in the Sixth Framework Programme".

Based on the key stakeholders identified on the mapping, interviews will be conducted for the realisation of the market outlook, in which, specific gender issues will be also analysed through ad-hoc questions, with the purpose to understand gender-sensitive needs for mobility services. ReNEW will also seek for contacts and engagement with relevant fora like the Women in Transport – Eu Platform.

In this sense, ReNEW seeks to bring the gender aspect by:

- Assessing possible project's impact on gender issues
- Integrating the topic in the dissemination and communication strategy to bring support across stakeholders
- Exchanging practices and experiences through interactive moments, such as workshops
- Engaging with women-led organisations whenever possible
- Support better understanding and defining gender use in the mobility infrastructure sector
- Considering gender balance in organised events
- Increasing gender balance in the project team
- Including gender balance in decision-making and project's Risk Assessment

- Monitoring and reporting progresses made on the topic

ReNEW project partners have committed to take measure to promote equal opportunities in the implementation of actions towards all the stakeholders involved in the project, including partners' organisations. Also, all public organisations partners commit to develop Gender Equality Plans, which includes integrating the gender dimension into R&I and teaching content in higher education institutions. By the end of the project, a total of 14 GEPs are expected, fulfilling the criteria as recommended by the Horizon Europe framework. The next deliverable, D5.2, will analyse the current GEPs, namely the organisation procedures, processes and practices integrating the gender dimension into R&I and teaching content in higher education institutions, this applies to all the public organisations' partners.

All material, on this topic, that is available and helpful will be made available for partners in the shared platform TEAMS.

3. Communication and dissemination tools

The ReNEW Communication and Dissemination tools are part of the Task 5.1 belonging to WP5 Outreach and Upscale.

T5.1: Dissemination and Communication is lead by Magellan with all partners and more specifically the Subtask ST5.1.1 Dissemination & Communication plan, material and website. The output of this task will be a detailed plan for communication and dissemination to achieve the ambitions of ReNEW.

This chapter namely provides an overview of the already established C&D tools at proposal stage and their revision in this document. It also sets the background and context for the tools that have been and are yet to be produced in the first months of the project life.

There are two types of communication and dissemination tools described in the following section. They can be differentiated between digital and printed tools in the order:

- Visual identity including project logo, colours, fonts and templates
- Website and social media
- Print materials including leaflets and roll-ups
- Standard presentation
- Videos
- Media relations content including press releases and articles

Once finalised and approved, all the C&D tools will be made available in the Teams depository used by the ReNEW partners.

3.1 Visual identity

The initial visual identity of the ReNEW project has been created just before the project kick-off in October 2022. The initial identity included the ReNEW logo, colours and fonts to be used in all materials and the working templates of the project (Word and Powerpoint). The logos, templates and brandbook are available on [Teams](#).

3.1.1 Logo

The first proposal of the ReNEW logo was initially proposed by the project coordinator and it included a blue wave and the title “ReNEW”. Magellan took over this task afterwards and the logo was updated and finalised together with a professional graphic design agency which created the full logo version.

The idea behind the ReNEW logo lies in representing a river, the main pathway of the inland transport waterways and its dynamics changing to a more sustainable future. The colours green and blue represent the colours of the water and the sustainable nature of the project.

Figure 8 ReNEW logo in colours

3.1.2 Templates

In addition to the logo, in the very early stage of the project, two templates were created to promote ReNEW and its brand identity in working documents: a Word template and a Powerpoint template. The Word template is available for use for deliverables and other working documents such as reports. The PowerPoint template, which includes the ReNEW graphic elements and present design forms, has been created for presentations at events and ReNEW’s project meetings, such as Work Package meetings and Living Lab workshops.

The templates have been circulated to the consortium partners for use and are available in the Teams depository. A standard ReNEW project PowerPoint presentation will be created and is further described in following section.

Figure 9 ReNEW Word Template

Figure 10 ReNEW Powerpoint Template

3.1.3 Signatures

An email signature design has been created for partners to use and to promote ReNEW to other stakeholders.

Figure 11 ReNEW signature for email

3.1.4 Brandbook

Colour, Font and EU Disclaimer Guidelines

Besides the official ReNEW logo, colour and font guidelines are to be respected whenever possible as per the colour palette below.

#007B6E
R: 0
G:123
B:110

#2494B6
R:36
G:148
B:182

#20396f
R:32
G:57
B:111

Figure 12 ReNEW primary colours

The Azonix Font will be used for headings and titles and any social media banners created with graphic programmes. The secondary font when Azonix is unavailable should be Roboto and should be used for the body of working documents such as deliverables and reports.

TYPOGRAPHY AZONIX

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
vwxyz
0123456789

Typography Roboto

Regular
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

Light
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

Medium
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

Bold
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

Black
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

Figure 13 ReNEW Primary and secondary fonts

The EU Funding Disclaimer will be clearly visible on all C&D materials, including banners, brochures, roll-ups, PowerPoint and Word templates. It has already been included on several ReNEW tools such as the website, Word and PPT templates.

Figure 14 ReNEW EC funding disclaimer example

3.2 Website

The ReNEW website is available at www.renew-waterways.eu. The website will serve as the main repository of project-related information, it will gather on different sections the project’s information, ReNEW’s purpose and objectives, consortium partners’ description, news, events, living labs information, hyperlinks to social media accounts, etc.

Google Analytics will be the tool to track the website traffic and monitor external interest in the project in order to get insightful information for the ongoing Communication Plan by identifying trends and patterns in how visitors engage with the content provided.

The full website structure is in the following order:

- Home
- About
- Newsroom
- Consortium
- Living Labs
- Contact
- Search tool

The ReNEW website homepage contains information on the project and its aims, the consortium partners, the latest news, and a call to action for external visitors to subscribe to ReNEW's newsletter - available also on all the other website pages.

Figure 15 ReNEW homepage

Figure 16 ReNEW footer

Figure 17 ReNEW website - about section

Figure 18 ReNEW website - Living Labs and LL1 example

Figure 19 ReNEW website - partner section

The ReNEW website will be available under the domain www.renew-waterways.eu. The website and the domain and in the ownership of Magellan and will be kept live during three years of the project as well as two years after the project end where it will host project results and outcomes (total of five years). The content management system is designed in WordPress, and the website is regularly

updated and managed by Magellan with the support of their graphic design and programmer for any complex updates.

3.3 Social media

Social media has great potential for reaching the target audiences of the project allowing for the creation of communities of support for the project’s key messages and objectives. ReNEW has created two social media accounts, Twitter and LinkedIn, just before the project kick-off, which were officially launched at the project kick-off, in October, with the first content. The two accounts will be regularly updated in accordance with the social media content strategy for the project.

The Twitter and LinkedIn accounts will use various types of content, including visual media, videos, info-graphics imagery, mobile-enabled content, and richer content experiences for users of any of the project’s digital platforms.

3.3.1 Twitter

The Twitter account is [@ReNEW_waterways](https://twitter.com/ReNEW_waterways). Magellan will regularly publish posts created with the help of the consortium.

Figure 20 ReNEW Twitter

3.3.2 LinkedIn

ReNEW has a company page found at www.linkedin.com/company/renew-inland-waterways/. Magellan is the account's administrator.

Figure 21 ReNEW LinkedIn post

3.3.3 Social media strategy

As mentioned above, different type of content will be used for ReNEW social media besides the main project results and outcomes.

The first stage of the project will see a social media campaign focused on the introduction and promotion of each ReNEW partner, their goals and role in the project.

The idea behind the strategy is to generate continuous content and buzz on the ReNEW channels even in a calmer period of the project, or before significant project results or events.

Table 2 ReNEW preliminary social media strategy

Strategy plan	Social media	Timeline	Notes
"Meet the partners" campaign	Twitter, LinkedIn	Once a week starting from 5 February 2023	Introducing each project partner description and role in the project
Living Labs introduction	Twitter, LinkedIn	Once a week starting 1 st week of March	Once LL webpages are ready, the presentation of each LL will start
Results / deliverables	Twitter, LinkedIn	When applicable	Once public deliverables have been approved by the Commission, dedicated posts will be made to announce achievements
Important dates	Twitter, LinkedIn	When applicable	More information in next table

Table 3 Social media campaigns outline

Date	Topic
8-Mar	Women's day
22-Mar	World Water Day
9-May	Europe Day
5-Jun	World Environment Day
20-22 Jun	European Sustainable Energy Week
11-15 September	Transport and Climate Change week
28-Sep	World Maritime Day
24 Sep	World Rivers Day

3.4 Standard presentation

A standard presentation has been created in order to be used at event and conferences to present ReNEW. The standard presentation will include a brief presentation of the project, its purpose, main goals and an explanation behind the Living Labs, which partners can also use for general presentations. Each partner is responsible to edit the presentation based on the need of the event where it will be used.

3.5 Newsletter

ReNEW will create a series of newsletters during the project life promoting news and main outcomes of the project in a specific period of time. A minimum of 2 newsletters is planned for every year of the project counting a total of 6 newsletters.

The mailing list will be created with the inputs of the project partners and the online platform that will be used will be Mailchimp.

3.6 Printed materials

Printed materials are one of the key C&D tools directed to address the target audiences at events and conferences. In the first month of the project, Magellan has already designed and produced a general roll up which was printed in 3 copies. The roll up was used for the project Kick-off in Brussels on 25 and 26 October 2022. The three roll-ups are currently stored at the IWT premises and will be used for future events.

Other roll-ups might be produced for the needs of events in the future. A general leaflet design is also planned to promote the project at events and conferences both in digital and printed form.

Figure 22 ReNEW general roll-up

3.7 Videos

Two types of videos are foreseen for the ReNEW project. A short, general, project presentation video will be produced to be shared with the media and will be uploaded on the project's social media channels. This video will be created in the mid-term of the project.

Second type of videos will be the those highlighting the Living Labs innovations, their challenges, vision and expected outcomes will be produced in the later months of the project.

Each of the 4 LLs will have the task of communicating its activities to the local audience. The promotion of the LLs innovations will be done through a series of short reportages which will also serve as tool for the general promotion of the project. A maximum of 8 video campaigns is foreseen in total divided by ½ short videos per Living Lab. A minimum of 1 video per Living Lab will be created.

3.8 Press and media

A series of press releases will be created to develop a close relationship with the media (journalists, specialised online media outlets, etc.). In addition to the typical press releases, to take the project's relationship with media a step further, full reports, summary reports, electronic and visual media will also be prepared that will be used for social media and the project website and newsletter. Generic project press release is foreseen to be created when there is news and results that could be interesting to the media. Given the activities in the Living Labs, at least two specific press releases to each pilot site will be created in the local language.

4. Events and conferences

Participation at conferences and fairs oriented to maritime and inland waterways stakeholders is of great importance for the outreach of ReNEW project. The list of potential events where ReNEW and its partners will consider attending is below. The WP leader will encourage and remind the partners on a monthly basis to revisit the list of events and see how to best organise the participation and promotion of ReNEW.

4.1 ReNEW Conferences and workshops

Besides attending external events the project ReNEW will organise two stakeholders' workshops and one major European conference (final event). Further, targeted local/national events and conferences will be attended using innovative ways, including video and digital media, to communicate the results of the project at these events. The partners will attend and present at relevant and high-profile conferences and networking events (national and international) to directly communicate to the key audiences. This will facilitate promotion, exchange of ideas, and feedback collection. The minimum of foreseen conference presentations and participations is 10.

The first series of workshops have been already organised, while several local workshops will also be organised in the LLs in the upcoming period. The project results will be presented in at least 10 international relevant conferences and events; a booth/stand will be set up in at least 3 relevant sector events.

Communication packages for LLs and promotional events will be carried out, and a major EU conference will be delivered in M24.

4.2 External events

The list below provides a preliminary list of events that are of potential interest to ReNEW project or its consortium members. These events will be shared and discussed with the partners and together with WP leader will evaluate whether of interest to attend and in line with budget.

Table 4 ReNEW list of preliminary external events

Date	Event	Location
2023		
16 March	Multimodal Transport Expo 2023	Breda, the Netherlands
20-24 March	Inland Shipping Week	Brussels, Belgium
9-12 May	Transport Logistic 2023	Munchen, Germany
23-25 May	Maritime Industry	Gorinchem, the Netherlands
24-25 May	European Maritime Day	Brest, France
24-25 May	Decarbonisation in Shipping: Europe 2023	Hamburg, Germany
31 May - 1 June	European Environmental Ports Conference	Valencia, Spain
1-2 June	ESPO Conference 2023	Bremen, Germany
10-11 June	International Conference on Port Management and Maritime Logistics	Barcelona, Spain
13-15 June	IPIC (International Physical Internet Conference)	Athens, Greece
20-21 June	European Inland Waterways Logistics Forum	Rotterdam, the Netherlands
26-30 June	RIS-Week	Stettin, Poland
26-27 September	European Waterborne days	Brussels, Belgium
10-12 October	Intermodal Europe 2023	Amsterdam, the Netherlands
tbd	European Research and Innovation Days 2022	tbd
2024		
15-18 April	Transport Research Arena Dublin	Dublin, Ireland
June	Connecting EU days	Barcelona, Spain
3-6 September	SMM – the leading international maritime trade fair	Hamburg, Germany

5. Publications and open science

A dedicated team will be established in the consortium under the management tasks (WP6), to oversee the related processes and make sure about compliance and best deployment of the developed knowledge. Such team will include a Data Management Office, Data Stewards and Data Custodians (INLE, AKKA, MAG, PNO), taking care of Open Access policies, appropriate classification of available data, choice of repositories and journals, Ethics and GDPR compliance, respect of Dissemination and Communication obligations, including the Consortium Agreement, to be defined. The team will release and update the project DMP (Data Management Plan). An outline of the above practices is defined below.

ReNEW will approach Open Science through the following key practices:

- early and open sharing of research, via open access to scientific publications under the conditions required by the Grant Agreement and open peer-review whenever possible.
- reproducibility of research outputs, tracking any research output or any other tools and instrument needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publications.
- responsible research data management in line with the FAIR20 principle.
- involving all relevant knowledge actors.

5.1 Zenodo Open Access

Zenodo has been chosen by the ReNEW partners as the Open Access platform for the ReNEW publications. Magellan has created an account for ReNEW on the Zenodo platform. The credentials have been shared with AKKA. A preview of the account is available in figure below.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo user interface. At the top, there is a blue navigation bar with the Zenodo logo, a search bar, and links for 'Upload' and 'Communities'. The user's email 'info@magellancircle.eu' is displayed in the top right corner. Below the navigation bar, a breadcrumb trail reads 'Home / Account / Profile'. On the left side, there is a 'Settings' menu with options: Profile (selected), Change password, Security, Linked accounts, Applications, Shared links, and GitHub. The main content area is titled 'Profile' and contains the following fields:

- Username:** ReNEW. A note below the field states: "Required. Username must start with a letter, be at least three characters long and only contain alphanumeric characters, dashes and underscores."
- Full name:** Resilient-centric Smart, Green, Networked EU Inland Waterways
- Email address:** info@magellancircle.eu
- Re-enter email address:** info@magellancircle.eu. A note below the field states: "Please re-enter your email address."

At the bottom of the profile form, there are two buttons: 'Cancel' and 'Update profile'.

Figure 23 ReNEW Zenodo Account

6. Management and roles

6.1 Partner roles

Each ReNEW partner has person months in WP5 and is expected to actively participate and contribute to the communication and dissemination of the ReNEW project and its results.

WP5 leader Magellan will regularly check if the partners are contributing to the dissemination and ensure the project goals and objectives are communicated properly using the ReNEW visual identity. For example, Magellan will encourage each partner to include the information about the ReNEW project on a dedicated page on their website including correct information and the ReNEW logo and a link to the ReNEW website.

6.2 Deliverables

Listed below are the main deliverables of WP5 Outreach and Upscale and their consequent updates.

D5.1: Dissemination and Communication Report [MAG] [A=M6; B=M18; C=M30; D=M36]

A) Stakeholders Analysis and Innovation Maps, an intelligence study by PNO to build the ground for the dissemination plan. It will include disaggregated data and a gender analysis among the innovators in the sector. Project communication and dissemination Strategy by MAG;

B) Periodic Activities Report.

C) Final Report.

D5.2: Innovation Management [INLE] [A=M18; B=M36]

A) Report detailing IP Management procedures; Report on IP management and Patents selection;

B) Report about patent filing for the marketable patents.

D5.3: Dissemination, Exploitation and Commercialisation Strategy and Plan [PNO] [A=M18; B=M24; C=M36]

D5.1. – Communication and Dissemination Report

- A) ReNEW ecosystem initiation plan and resilience and sustainability roadmap, exploitation activities report summary.
- B) Market analysis, a report by PNO to identify the key trends in the project innovation landscape and provide market information, and business models and commercialisation plan.
- C) Final Report detailing the innovation and summary of related exploitation activities having been conducted. Commercialisation Plan update.

D5.4: Capacity Building and Policy Recommendations [VIL] [A=M18; B=M36]

- A) Report collating initial capacity building progress.
- B) Final report collating all current and ongoing activities. Recommendations Report.

6.3 Editorial calendar

In order to implement all C&D tools in the best possible way and to ensure coherent dissemination with regular content, the WP leader has created a preliminary editorial calendar. The editorial calendar consists of a detailed plan of how often these C&D activities will take place in a monthly or quarterly basis. The calendar will mostly social media activities and planned newsletters and their content.

The calendar will be fed with information regularly thanks to the input of all partners, with the close collaboration with the WP leaders.

Table 5 Editorial Calendar

Publish Date	Topic / Title	Target audience	Channels
2022			
26-Oct	Kick-off the new Horizon Europe project - ReNEW	all	LinkedIn, Twitter
26-Oct	Kick-off event of ReNEW project - day 1	all	LinkedIn, Twitter
27-Oct	Kick-off event of ReNEW project - day 2	all	LinkedIn, Twitter
8-Nov	Project coordinator Nik Delmeire of IWT interview to Magellan Circle Journal podcast series	all	LinkedIn, Twitter
23-Dez	Happy Holidays from ReNEW	all	LinkedIn, Twitter

2023			
6-Feb	Meet our partners - IWT	all	LinkedIn , Twitter
10-Feb	Living Lab 2 - workshop	all	LinkedIn , Twitter
14-Feb	Living Lab 3 - workshop	all	LinkedIn , Twitter
17-Feb	Living Lab 1 - workshop	all	LinkedIn , Twitter

7. Monitoring and KPIs

This communication and dissemination plan will be regularly assessed during the project runtime. The minimum measurable results have been established at the project proposal stage. Table 7, below, describes the quantitative targets for each of the dissemination and communication activities described above. The table has been revised in line with the updated communication strategy of this document and now indicates updated figures from the Grant Agreement.

Table 6 C&D objectives and KPIs

C&D Tool	Objective	Measurable result (KPI)
Visual identity and printed materials	To create a coherent and catchy project brand identity, a logo, templates for presentations (e.g. for conferences), internal and external documents (e.g. report templates).	Creation of a project logo and accompanying visual identity elements including banners for social media and website, creation of templates for presentations and deliverables.
Website	A project website, serving as the main repository of project-related information, will be created and regularly updated (with sections such as project information, news, Living labs, results, partners, events, hyperlinks to social media, etc.). Google Analytics will be used to track the website traffic and monitor external interest in the project.	Project website (due in Month 3 with continuous updates) with at least 3000 unique visits till the end of the project.
Social Media	The project will have a strong social media presence through the creation of Twitter and LinkedIn pages, using visual media based on the projects' visual identity, videos and info-graphic imagery created with the input of the LLs. Further, a social media grid with	Over 300 Twitter followers and 500 members on LinkedIn Group. All of the social media posts will generate at least 10 useful interactions/

	the corresponding social media channels, targeted specific audiences and messages will be prepared within the scope of D5.1	conversations per month with the linked stakeholders.
Living Labs short Video Campaigns	Each of the 4 LLs will have the task of communicating its activities to the local audience. The promotion of the LLs innovations will be done through a series of short reportages which will also serve as tool for the general promotion of the project.	1/2 short video per LL (leader and users) which counts for 8 video campaigns in total. The KPI for each local video is 150 views at minimum.
Media Relations	A series of press releases will be created to develop a close relationship with the media (journalists, specialised online media outlets, etc.). In addition to the typical press releases, to take the project's relationship with media a step further, full reports, summary reports, electronic and visual media will also be prepared.	3 generic project Press Releases and at least 2 press releases specific to each pilot site (local language).
Project symposium, outreach & networking	The project will organise 2 stakeholders symposium. Further, targeted local/national events and conferences will be attended using innovative ways, including video and digital media, to communicate the results of the project at these events. The partners will attend and present at relevant and high-profile conferences and networking events (national and international) to directly communicate to the key audiences. This will facilitate promotion, exchange of ideas, and feedback collection.	Several local workshops will be organised in the LLs. The project results will be presented in at least 10 international relevant conferences and events; a both/stand will be set up in at least 3 relevant sector events.
Newsletter	The newsletter will include news and updates on the project and relevant associated events.	At least 6 e-newsletters will be sent out throughout the project duration.
Video	A short project presentation video will be produced to be shared with the media and will be uploaded on the project's social media channels.	Over 800 video views across all platforms in which it will be shown/uploaded.

7.1 C&D Monitoring tool

ReNEW will keep track of all the communication and dissemination activities done within the project whether it is an article about ReNEW published on the web, or a presentation done by a partner in an external event.

The partners will be reminded on a monthly basis to fill in the information in the so-called monitoring sheet. The structure of the tool is self-explanatory and easy for partners to fill in the information. The C&D monitoring tool is available on [Teams](#) and partners can access it and edit in real time.

The table below shows a part of the C&D monitoring tool and the information it includes. The original table has additional columns for comments and the impact referring to the number of participants addressed and audience type.

Table 7 ReNEW C&D Monitoring Tool

ReNEW Communication and dissemination activities					
Year	Month / Date	Title	Type of activity (presentation, article, press release, participation at event, interview, etc.)	Partners involved	Links
2022	08-Nov	Inland Waterways Transport with Nik Delmeire, IWT	Podcast episode	IWT & Magellan	Podcast list

8. Cross-cooperation with other projects

ReNEW project responded to the Call: HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01 (Safe, Resilient Transport and Smart Mobility services for passengers and goods) together with PLOTO - Deployment and Assessment of Predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against Climate change and other extremes - and CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways - under the Horizon Europe programme. The 3 projects share common challenges and aim to establish a strong cooperation along their life span.

PLOTO aims to enhance the resilience of Inland WaterWays (IWW) infrastructures and land-based infrastructures for reliable network availability during extreme weather and other hazards. The project integrates climate change scenarios, simulation tools, and actual data to provide effective infrastructure management. PLOTO uses high-resolution modelling data and new sensor-generated data to assess climatic risks, provide weather forecasts and develop robust spectral analysis, computer vision and machine learning-based assessments. PLOTO designs an integrated Resilience Assessment Platform and a Common Operational Picture for better visualization and incident management. The platform and tools will be validated through case studies in Belgium, Romania, and Hungary.

CRISTAL aims to increase freight transport on inland waterways by 20% and improve reliability by 80% in pilot sites in Italy, Poland, and France. It will test and implement innovative solutions using technology, digitalization, and advancements towards the Physical Internet. The project has garnered considerable interest from the intermodal environment as Polish rivers face significant navigability problems. The success of the CRISTAL project is expected to improve navigability, infrastructure, and reliability for inland waterway transport in Europe.

There are high expectations for PLOTO, CRISTAL, and ReNEW projects to benefit from each other's activities and outcomes to improve the efficiency, resilience, and sustainability of transport systems, both in urban areas and inland waterways, against natural and man-made disasters. ReNEW project's focus on building a sustainable and resilient inland waterway transport (IWT) sector in Europe through various activities, including the creation of innovative infrastructure solutions, decision-support frameworks, and a green IWT dataspace, complements the objectives of PLOTO and CRISTAL projects.

PLOTO project is aimed at improving the efficiency, resilience, and sustainability of multimodal transport systems in urban areas. The Living Lab 1 of ReNEW project, which is focused on creating a flexible and resilient logistic system for multi-user and multifunctional purposes, aligns with the objectives of PLOTO project by developing Synchronodal Logistics Hubs in the city of Ghent. These

projects can reinforce each other in the area of the innovative infrastructure solutions and autonomy developments that are being implemented in the Living Lab 1 of ReNEW project.

On the other hand, CRISTAL project is aimed at improving the resilience and safety of critical infrastructure systems, including transport systems, against natural and man-made disasters. ReNEW project's IWT Resilience and Sustainability decision-support framework and probabilistic risk and safety analyses can be utilized by the CRISTAL project to improve the resilience of transport systems against extreme weather events and other disasters. Additionally, the Living Labs of ReNEW project, which are focused on testing and demonstrating the resilience of IWT systems, can provide valuable insights to CRISTAL project, which is focused on improving the resilience of critical infrastructure systems.

To leverage on possible synergies the meetings, workshops, and common participation in events are foreseen. The first contacts with the respective projects were initiated and led to the common participation in the upcoming event in the frame of "Inland Navigation Week 2023". It will take place on 21 March 2023 in hybrid mode.

Other cross-cooperation opportunities are currently investigated. One of them is the participation in the regular "Joint EU Smart Shipping & Logistics Platform" meetings between EU Horizon projects. During these meetings, new projects relevant to smart shipping and logistics are introduced to the community and opportunities for joint activities are considered.

9. Conclusions

This document describes the updated communication and dissemination plan, of which the original draft version was presented at proposal stage. The document consists of several chapters including the most important actions and strategies for a coherent and effective communication and dissemination of ReNEW project objectives and results. Detailed descriptions of both already existing digital and printed tools and those to yet be created are accompanied by the lists of preliminary channels and instruments for dissemination.

This document not only serves as a report but also as the main guideline document for all the ReNEW project partners which are all responsible for the most successful communication of the project, under the management of the WP5 leader.

Special importance in the document is given to the management and monitoring of the C&D actions and the expected KPIs. This strategy is a living document which will be revisited on a regular basis. The results of the tools used will be regularly monitored and action will be taken if the set criteria are not met.

10. References

[FlowPaper AdaptiveUI \(europa.eu\)](#)

[Tackling gender equality in Research and Innovation \(europa.eu\)](#)

[Gender equality in research and innovation \(europa.eu\)](#)

[GENDERACTION_WP3_final_report.pdf](#)